

Magnetoelectric coupling in antiferromagnet $\text{Co}_4\text{Ta}_2\text{O}_9$

S. Chaudhary, P. Srivastava and S. Patnaik*

School of Physical Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi-110067, India

Email id : spatnaikjnu@gmail.com

Abstract

We study the magnetoelectric (ME) coupling in spin-flop driven antiferromagnet $\text{Co}_4\text{Ta}_2\text{O}_9$. The dielectric constant and pyroelectric current show features associated with ferroelectric transitions at the antiferromagnetic transition temperature ($T_N = 20$ K). The effect of magnetic field is to enhance the features almost linearly up to the maximum measured field (6 T) with a saturation polarization value of $52 \mu\text{C}/\text{m}^2$.

Keywords: Magnetoelectric materials, Electric polarization, Magnetization.

References:

1. J. F. Scott et al, Science 315(2007) 954.
2. M. Bibes et al, Nature Mater. 7(2008)425
3. Y. Fang et al, J. Am. Ceram. Soc. 98(2015)2005.
4. I. V. Solovyev et al, Phy. Rev. B 94(2016)094427